

Optimisation of reduction parameters of NiCl₂ to Ni in the gel matrix

K. Basu^{a*}, K. Biswas^b, G. C. Das^c, S. Mukherjee^c and M. K. Mitra^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Bankim Sardar College, Tangrakhali-743 329, 24-Parganas (S), West Bengal, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Berhampur Girl's College, Berhampur-742 101, Murshidabad, West Bengal, India

^cCentre for Nanoscience and Technology, School of Material Science and Technology, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

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Abstract : A glass metal nano composite where the second phase metal is of nanometric size (10^{-9} m) is prepared. The properties of nano composites are the function of shape, size and distribution of the metallic phase present. The identification of the shape, size and distribution of the metallic particles can be obtained from Transmission Electron Micro structure analysis (TEM). Controlling various process parameters like temperature of the reaction site, composition of the reductant, ratio of the metal to the matrix and the time taken for the maximum and minimum reductions, experiments were carried out according to a statistical plan technique to optimize the parameters of reduction of metal salt NiCl₂ to metal Ni. To know the mechanistic aspects of reduction and for the optimization of the reduction parameters analysis have been carried out.

Keywords : Gel matrix, reduction parameters, nickel(II) chloride.

The nano crystalline material is defined as the material having grain size in the range of 1 nm to about 100 nm, at least in one dimension. This material is variously known as nano crystals, nano structure material, nano phase material or nanometer sized crystalline solids. Nano structure material is in a non equilibrium state of condensed matter. The structure and properties of these materials are not only function of chemical composition, shape and size of crystallites but are also strongly depended on the mode of preparation and their thermal history. These nano composites can be prepared through sol-gel route¹ by reducing metallic species present in the matrix by the generation of H₂ *in situ*² or from outside³. Previous results have been reported⁴ on *in situ* isothermal reduction kinetics of the NiCl₂ - containing gel. The present paper deals with systematic study of the preparation of nano composite under isothermal condition for assessing and controlling the various process parameters like temperature of the reaction site, amount of the dextrose, time of reaction, ratio of alcohol. Experiments were performed according to a statistically planned technique of experimental design. This technique has the advantage of yielding optimum condition in a relatively smaller number of experiments. A regression equation is formed from which the influence of each process variable and its relative influence can be readily assessed.

Results and discussion

In order to prepare glass-metal nano composites without melting via the sol-gel route by *in situ* reduction of metallic salts in the silica gel matrix following steps were first taken.

(i) A precursor solution of ethyl alcohol and TEOS was made.

(ii) Another solution containing NiCl₂, water, dextrose and ethyl alcohol was prepared which was slowly added to the other on constant stirring at 22° C.

(iii) The resultant solution was kept for gelling for 6-7 days at room temperature. The following statistical design matrix condition (Table 1) was maintained in course of preparation of gel as also in the experiments.

For other three samples amount of dextrose is 25% and the ratio of TEOS : H₂O : alcohol is 1 : 1 : 2.5. The samples were kept for several days for attaining the required dryness at room temperature and the calculated amount (10%) of NiCl₂ was maintained in all the samples.

The reduction experiment was carried out under constant flow of dry nitrogen in a programmable electric furnace with PID controller. The amount of water content of the samples had been kept constant by check-measurement of the weight of the samples before inser-

Table 1. Composition of gel matrix containing 10 wt% NiCl₂ at different temperatures

Level	Experimental parameters				
	%Reductant (Dextrose)	Temp. (°C)	Time for reduction (min)	TEOS : H ₂ O : Ethyl alcohol	Code
High	50% excess	950	6	1 : 1 : 3	+1
Low	Stoichiometric	850	1	1 : 1 : 2	-1
Base	25% excess	900	3	1 : 1 : 2.5	0

Table 2. Design matrix for the reduction experiment taking the different experimental parameters

Sl. no.	Time (x ₁)	Dextrose (x ₂)	Temp. (x ₃)	Comp. (x ₄)
1.	-1	+1	+1	+1
2.	-1	+1	+1	-1
3.	+1	+1	+1	+1
4.	+1	+1	+1	-1
5.	-1	-1	+1	+1
6.	-1	-1	+1	-1
7.	+1	-1	+1	+1
8.	+1	-1	+1	-1
9.	-1	+1	-1	+1
10.	-1	+1	-1	-1
11.	+1	+1	-1	+1
12.	+1	+1	-1	-1
13.	-1	-1	-1	+1
14.	-1	-1	-1	-1
15.	+1	-1	-1	+1
16.	+1	-1	-1	-1

tion in the furnace. The HCl vapour was generated as a result of reduction of NiCl₂ by *in situ* generated hydrogen of the decomposed dextrose, following the mechanism

The HCl so generated was swept away by oxygen and moisture free N₂ gas which was made to bubble through known volume of doubly distilled water in absorbing tower. HCl vapour was absorbed for a fixed interval of time. The subsequent measurement of pH of the solution gave the fraction of metal reduced, as the initial amount of NiCl₂ in the gel sample was known. Kinetic data obtained in the following experiments were investigated and graphs drawn (Figs. 1a and 1b).

Fig. 1(a). Plot of fraction converted (α) vs time of NiCl₂ containing gels with TEOS : C₂H₅OH = 1 : 3 by volume and 50% extra dextrose : (▲) 950 °C, (■) 850 °C.

Fig. 1(b). Plot of fraction converted (α) vs time of NiCl₂ containing gels with TEOS : C₂H₅OH = 1 : 2 by volume and stoichiometric dextrose : (●) 950 °C, (■) 850 °C.

From the kinetic experiment it was observed that the gel where TEOS : C₂H₅OH ratio is 1 : 2 and a stoichiometric amount of dextrose present, the fractional conversion is higher than where the gel with TEOS : C₂H₅OH ratio is 1 : 2 and amount of dextrose present is 50% excess. This happens because of the fact that the interconnected pore within the gel matrix get more filled up

by increasing the amount of reductant and thereby the free space available for gases such as HCl and unreacted hydrogen that diffuse out of the system decreases. So the rate as well as extent of overall conversion decreases. In case of stoichiometric dextrose present in the gel the pores are occupied in lesser extent. Thus resistance offered to the passage of product gases to diffuse out is also less – speeding up the reaction rate and increasing overall percentage of conversion. Gels with TEOS : C₂H₅OH ratio 1 : 3 exhibit a slower rate of conversion and lower fractional conversion with stoichiometric dextrose than gels containing 50% excess dextrose. This behavior is exactly opposite to that of gels where TEOS : C₂H₅OH ratio is 1 : 2. This is because of the fact that with the increase in the amount of alcohol, the average pores size and percentage of porosity increases to a large extent. This means the amount of hydrogen available for reduction will decrease. It was also observed that fractional conversion for a particular composition of the gel would vary with temperature. As the temperature increases the fractional conversion increases.

As the reduction experiments were performed according to a statistically planned technique of experimental design, it had the advantage of yielding optimum condition, even in a smaller number of experiment, and a regression equation could also be formed for assessing the relative influence of each variable of the process. Further, in order to ascertain the appropriate reaction mechanism the experimental data on time dependent fractional conversion have been analysed by the theoretical reduced time plots (Fig. 2). For a particular mechanism

$$g(\alpha) = kt \tag{i}$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is an appropriate function of fractional conversion (α), which depends on the type of reaction mechanisms as outlined in Table 3.

$$\text{For } \alpha = 0.3, g(0.3) = kt_{0.3} \tag{ii}$$

where $t_{0.3}$ is the time required for 0.3 fractional conversion.

Dividing eqs. (i) by (ii) we get

$$g(\alpha)/g(0.3) = t/t_{0.3} = \theta \tag{iii}$$

θ is reduced time — a dimensionless quantity. From eq. (iii) we see that α vs θ plot is independent of k , which is temperature dependant term in kinetics. The computed α vs θ plot from experimental data will coincide with that of theoretical α vs θ plot. Therefore, by comparing the computed α vs θ plot from experimental data with theoretically computed plots for different gas solid reactions, we can find which mechanism is operative. X-Ray dif-

Table 3. Kinetic models of gas solid reactions

Symbol	Name	Form of $g(\alpha)$
D 1	Parabolic	α^2
CG 1	Linear growth	α
CG 2	Cylindrical	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/2}]$
CG 3	Spherical symmetry	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]$
NG 1	Avrami Erofeev	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)]^{2/3}$
NG 2	Avrami Erofeev	$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/2}$
NG 3	Avrami Erofeev	$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/3}$

α = fraction converted.

Fig. 2. Plot of fraction converted (α) vs reduced time (θ): (1) NG-3, (2) NG-2, (3) NG-1, (4) CG₁, (5) CG₃, (6) sample, (7) D₁.

fraction studies of four reduced samples were carried out where the extremities of temperature and composition of dextrose was considered. The inter planner spacing have been computed using Bragg's law. The computed d_{hkl} has been compared with the standard d_{hkl} values of Ni and NiO. The four reduced samples (no. 3, 7, 11, 13) gave the same set of defraction peaks. The Fig. 3 shows typical XRD pattern for a reduced sample. The identified phases have been marked along side the peaks. The average particle size for different samples was calculated from the equation,

$$t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B \cos \theta_B}$$

where t is the average particle size in Å, B is the width of

peak at half the peak height in radians, λ is the wavelength of X-rays and θ_B is the Bragg angle in degree. The computed particle size is about 15 nm. Fig. 4 shows TEM photograph of reduced samples having the magnification bar. From the figure the average size of the Ni is found 8 nm. Fig. 5 shows typical SEM photograph (of the same sample that of TEM). The four reduced samples (no. 3, 7, 11, 13) gave the same set of diffraction peaks. There is a distinct long height peak observed in the lower region (Fig. 3). TEM analysis was also performed for the sample

after reduction at 950 °C with the ratio of TEOS : C₂H₅OH is 1 : 3 and stoichiometric amount of dextrose was present (Fig. 4).

Experimental

SiO₂ gels containing a calculated amount (10 wt%) of NiCl₂ and 1.5 times/stoichiometric dextrose as the reductant were prepared separately from solution containing tetraethyl ortho silicate and the metal chloride in ethyl alcohol and water solution. All the reagents used in the

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of 10 wt% nickel reduced at 950 °C Sample no 7

Fig. 4. TEM photograph of sample no. 7 after reduction at 950 °C.

Fig. 5. Scanning Electron Micrograph of reduced sample (sample no. 7) at 950 °C.

experiments were of analytical grade. The concentration of the metal chloride in the solution was adjusted to yield 10% of metal with respect to the host silica matrix. The volume ratio of ethyl alcohol solution containing metal chloride and TEOS were maintained at 3 : 1 for 8 gel samples and 2 : 1 for another 8 samples and 3 base gels samples of 2.5 : 1 composition were also prepared. The gels prepared were converted to Ni-SiO₂ *in situ* nano composition by isothermal reduction treatment under N₂ atmosphere. The experimental temperature (850 °C, 950 °C), reduction time, amount of dextrose and stoichiometric and wt% metal to be liberated by non isothermal reduction were considered as input variables. Care has been taken to control the initial water content in the gel samples by weighing the samples just before insertion. The recorded insertion weight was kept nearly constant for all the experimental samples. This isothermal reduction experiments were carried out in a programmable electric heating furnace with PID controller.

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